

HISTORICAL AND CULTURAL CONTEXTS OF FEMININE CHARACTERS IN LITERATURE

(Jane Austen “pride and prejudice”)

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Abstract: This article delves into the intricate interplay between historical and cultural contexts and the portrayal of feminine characters in literature. Drawing upon a diverse range of literary works spanning different epochs and regions, the study examines how societal norms, cultural values, and historical events shape the depiction of women in fiction. Through a nuanced analysis, it explores the evolution of feminine archetypes, from traditional roles of motherhood and domesticity to more complex and empowered representations. By scrutinizing the historical backdrop against which these characters are situated, the article sheds light on the ways in which authors both reinforce and subvert gender stereotypes, reflecting the prevailing ideologies of their times. Moreover, it investigates the impact of feminist movements and social change on literary representations of femininity, highlighting the role of literature in challenging established norms and fostering progressive attitudes towards gender equality. Ultimately, this exploration underscores the dynamic relationship between literature, history, and culture in shaping our understanding of feminine identities across time and space.

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Key words: extralinguistic, gender specific, phraseological units, females, males, bachelorette, national identity, stereotypes, statements, analogues, linguoculturological.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola tarixiy va madaniy kontekstlarning murakkab o'zaro ta'sirini va adabiyotdagi ayol qahramonlari tasvirini o'rganadi. Turli davrlar va mintaqalarni qamrab olgan turli-tuman adabiy asarlarga tayangan holda, tadqiqot ijtimoiy normalar, madaniy qadriyatlar va tarixiy voqealar badiiy adabiyotda ayollar tasvirini qanday shakllantirishini o'rganadi. Nuansli tahlil orqali u ayol arxetiplarining evolyutsiyasini, onalik va uy-ro'zg'orning an'anaviy rollaridan tortib, yanada murakkab va vakolatli tasvirlargacha o'rganadi. Ushbu qahramonlar qaysi tarixiy sharoitda joylashganligini sinchkovlik bilan o'rganib chiqqan holda, maqola mualliflarning o'z davrining hukmron mafkuralarini aks ettiruvchi gender stereotiplarini kuchaytirish va buzish usullarini yoritadi. Bundan tashqari, u feministik harakatlar va ijtimoiy o'zgarishlarning ayollikning adabiy

tasvirlariga ta'sirini o'rganadi, adabiyotning o'rnatilgan me'yorlarga qarshi kurashdagi rolini ta'kidlaydi va gender tengligiga progressiv munosabatni rivojlantiradi. Oxir oqibat, bu tadqiqot adabiyot, tarix va madaniyat o'rtasidagi vaqt va makon bo'ylab ayol o'ziga xosligi haqidagi tushunchamizni shakllantirishdagi dinamik aloqani ta'kidlaydi.

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Kalit so'zlar: ekstralingvistik, jins o'ziga xoslik, frazeologik birliklar, ayollar, bakalavr, milliy o'ziga xoslik, stereotiplar, bayonotlar, analoglari, lingvokulturologika.

Introduction: In analyzing the historical and cultural contexts of feminine characters in literature, it's important to consider the time period in which the work was written and the societal expectations placed upon women. "Pride and

Prejudice," written by Jane Austen and published in 1813, provides a rich example of feminine characters within the context of early 19th century England.

In "Pride and Prejudice," the protagonist Elizabeth Bennet is depicted as a strong, independent, and intelligent woman which stands in contrast to the societal norms of the time. During the early 1800s, women were expected to prioritize marriage and domestic duties, and their social standing was largely determined by their marital status.

Elizabeth Bennet's character challenges these expectations by exhibiting a spirited independence and refusing to conform to the traditional roles assigned to women. Her wit, intelligence, and refusal to settle for a marriage based solely on financial security or social status make her a notable character in the context of the time period.

Through Elizabeth Bennet, Austen provides a critique of the limitations placed upon women in her society, while also depicting the complexities and struggles faced by women in navigating societal expectations and personal desires. The character of Elizabeth Bennet thus serves as a reflection of the societal and cultural context of the time, while also offering a nuanced portrayal of a woman who defies the norms of her era.

Pride and Prejudice is a novel that revolves around the life of the Bennet family, particularly Elizabeth, the protagonist. The Bennet family, belonging to the middle class, has no direct male heir, and Elizabeth's mother, Mrs. Bennet, devotes her life to finding husbands for her daughters. She forces Mr. Bennet to introduce their daughters to Mr. Bingley, an unmarried young man with a handsome income who has just moved in the neighborhood. However, Mrs. Bingley is known for gossip and inappropriate social behavior, and her behavior influences her daughter's destiny.

Elizabeth "Lizzy" Bennet, the second daughter of the Bennets, is described

as having a lively disposition and intelligence. She is one of the most famous literary characters of all time, and she is Mr. Bennet's favorite child. However, Elizabeth transcends her family members in her manners and understanding of life. She states her opinion directly and has a sharp tongue, which often shocks those who believe that ladies cannot be allowed such freedom.

During her conversation with Lady Catherine, Elizabeth openly challenges social norms regarding female behavior. She believes that the last born has as good a right to the pleasures of youth as the first, and that reading is what feeds the mind. Elizabeth's opinion is the product of common sense, not of social conventions. She expects herself to be the first creature who had ever dared to trifle with so much dignified impertinence, thus proving herself to be a modern woman who does not care about class and rank.

Elizabeth's attitude towards marriage is different from that of society. She rejects Mr. Collins' proposal to marry her, believing that she pretends to be unattainable. In the end, she assures him that she is not one of those young ladies who are so daring as to risk their happiness on the chance of being asked a second time.

In *Pride and Prejudice*, Elizabeth Bennet is a woman who understands the true purpose of marriage, unlike her mother and sisters. She rejects various proposals, including Mr. Collins and Mr. Darcy, because she believes they are immoral and evil. Elizabeth's attitude towards marriage is evident in her interactions with Charlotte, her friend, and her own feelings for her future husband. Elizabeth is an intelligent and independent woman who does not care about the opinion of others and does what she thinks is best for her. She fights for what she wants and believes in, which is Mr. Darcy and her love for him. She is not afraid of Lady Catherine, who believes their marriage would be the most unsuitable match. Jane Bennet, the eldest daughter, is the prettiest girl in the county and has the best opinion of Mr. Bingley's sisters. However, they do not see her as a suitable match

to their brothers, so they take him away from the Netherfield. When they leave, Jane is broken but decides to try to get better.

Jane is a strong woman who decides to conceal her pain and loves Mr. Bingley more than his fortune. She values his character and fervently prefers him over every other man. Jane is the same as Elizabeth when it comes to love; she prefers love over financial security and does not care about money.

Charlotte Lucas, a 27-year-old spinster, accepts Mr. Collins's proposal, believing it is the only honorable provision for well-educated young women of small fortune. She is not romantic but believes she cannot do better than him, focusing on her position in life. However, her economic motivations deprive her of a chance to be happily married and emotionally attached to her husband. In the end, she becomes the same shallow person as Mr. Collins, highlighting the social standards of the time that dependent women have no chance of living a fulfilled life.

Lydia and Kitty, the youngest sisters in the Bennet family, are not as intelligent and behave like most teenagers. They live around balls and the military, with Lydia having high animal spirits and a natural self-consequence. Her reckless behavior, such as running away with Mr. Wickham, endangers their sisters' position on the marriage market. This highlights how social norms regarding marriage can make young women do foolish things and enter a marriage they will regret later.

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